

MANUFACTURE AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CF-CNT PAPER REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES BY RESIN INFUSION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube materials have excellent mechanical, thermal and electrical properties, characteristics that make them interesting for potential applications in the electronics, aerospace industry [1]. In particular, Carbon nanotube paper (CNP)/polymer composites are potential candidates for lightweight multifunctional structural materials with high mechanical performance. CNP is typically fabricated by filtering aqueous suspensions of CNTs [2]. We report that carbon aqueous dispersion could be manufactured using ultra-sonication and that these show dramatic improvements in electrical conductivity with percolation threshold $\sim 0.2\%$ of MWNT. By significantly improving the dispersion of MWNTs, we show that only a very small amount of MWNTs are needed to achieve the conductivity levels required for different electrical applications. Chopped carbon fibers aqueous dispersion can be dispersed using ozon treatment. CF-CNT paper can be fabricated by wet-laying of mixed CF-CNT aqueous dispersion. CF-CNT papers were embedded in epoxy resin by resin infusion process to realize CNT/Epoxy composites. In this study, we report that electrical conductivity measurements of the CF-CNT papers and mechanical properties of the paper and their polymer composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The problems of global warming and high oil prices in modern society are demanding light weight and durability of transportation vehicles. Therefore, the technology for a fiber reinforced polymer composite material, which is a combination of high performance carbon fibers and polymers, has been actively developed for the weight reduction of interior, exterior, and structural materials for the transportation vehicles. In addition, the gradual adoption of the electronic equipment in the vehicles increases the emission amount of electromagnetic wave, resulting in a safety accident of malfunction of electronic components. To overcome these problems, the studies of a light weight carbon/polymer composite material for electromagnetic wave shielding for transporting vehicle components are required.

Nonwovens are widely used in the automotive industry due to their excellent properties such as flexibility, lightness, easy formability, recyclability, variety of materials and low processing costs. In particular, wet-laid nonwoven fabrics can be produced a desired type of fiber structure having a fabric characteristic such as flexibility and strength at a high speed such as paper production speed. The wet-laid nonwoven fabrics are produced by dispersing the fibers in water through a dissolution and dissociation process, and then obtaining a uniform sheet-like fiber structure by using a paper machine. It is possible to manufacture environmentally friendly nonwoven fabrics using water as an initial solvent. In addition, the fibers used in the wet-laid nonwoven fabrics have a relatively short fiber length as compared with other nonwoven fabrication processes, so that there is no limitation on the raw fibers, and therefore, carbon fibers and carbon nanotubes (CNT) are suitable for making nonwoven fabrics [3,4].

CNTs have been studied because of their unique structure, high chemical stability and optical, electrical and mechanical properties [5]. The high aspect ratio of the CNT causes the CNT to form bundles and intertwine with each other [6]. In addition, CNT are attracted strongly within the bundle due to the high van der waals interaction between the tubes [7]. The low dispersibility of CNT in water

dispersion makes it difficult to manufacture CNT Buckypaper by wet-laid process. In order to ensure the dispersibility of carbon fibers and multi-walled carbon nanotubes in the wet-laid nonwoven manufacturing process, the dispersibility was evaluated in terms of dispersant content, types, and dispersion methods to manufacture CF-CNT nonwoven fabrics by the optimum process condition.

VARIM (Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion Molding) process, one of the composites manufacturing processes, has been extensively studied for cost reduction as compared with prepreg technology which requires autoclave process for curing process [8-10].

In this study, CF and CNT nonwoven fabrics were prepared by various dispersing methods through wet process, and composite material was prepared by impregnating epoxy with VARIM process. The properties of nonwoven fabrics and composites were evaluated to investigate the feasibility of using fiber reinforced polymer composites for lightweight interior and exterior materials and structural materials of transportation vehicles.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNT) fabricated by a CVD method were purchased from Hanwha Chem. Co., Ltd. Of Daejeon, Korea (10–15 nm in diameter, up to 200 μm in length, and purity >97 wt%, CM-280). The surfactant Kolliphor P 188 (Koll), the polymer stabilizer Polystyrene sulfonate (PSS), and Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received without further purification. Carbon fiber (CF, T700SC, 12K, 800tex) purchased from Toray. Co., Ltd. of Japan, was chopped 6mm in length and used. The polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fiber used as a binder in the preparation of carbon fiber nonwoven fabrics purchased from Kuraray Co., Ltd. of Japan, were chopped 6 mm in length and used. To fabricate CF-CNT composites, epoxy resin (Epoxy resin 1050, RESOLTECH, France) and epoxy hardener (Epoxy hardener 1056S, RESOLTECH, France) were used. The carbon fiber 3 K plain weave fabrics of Hyundai Fiber Co. were used as reinforcing fibers to increase the tensile strength in the production of thermosetting composite material.

2.2 Preparation of specimen

In the nonwoven fabrics fabrication process using the Wet-laid process, 1L of water was filled in the pulper, 2g of CF and PVA (10 wt.% of CF) were added as a binder, Koll was added as a dispersing agent, and the mixing and dispersion process was performed at a speed of 300 rpm for 1 hour. In order to improve the dispersibility of the CF on the water dispersion, an ozone generator was injected into a pulp process in which CF and PVA were mixed and dispersed to observe dispersibility according to ozone treatment time, and ozone generator generates ozone of 300 mg per hour. 2 g of CNT were dispersed by mechanical stirring for 24 hours in 1 L of distilled water in which dispersant Koll was dissolved. The dispersion was ultra-sonicated for 30 min with VCX1500 sonicator at 1500W 200kHz. Electrical conductivities of five CF-CNT aqueous dispersion with CNT concentrations ranging from 1 to 50 wt% were compared in this study. The CF-CNT nonwoven papers were fabricated using the laboratory scale hand sheet former from the prepared CNT dispersions. After filtration, the paper was dried for 24 h in room temperature and for 72 h in 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a convection oven. The CF-CNT preforms were infiltrated with epoxy using vacuum-assisted resin infusion moulding (VARIM). The epoxy resin was mixed with the curing agent at 100/35 parts by weight. Prior to impregnation, the epoxy resin system was degassed in a vacuum oven for about 20 min to remove entrapped air bubbles and was heated to 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to lower the viscosity. In the VARIM process, illustrated in Figure 1, the CF-CNT preform was sealed in a vacuum bag and sealant tapes, and the epoxy resin was then infused into the CF-CNT preform under vacuum. After the infiltration of epoxy, the composites were cured for 16 h at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 1: Composite material manufacturing method using VARIM technique

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 CNT dispersion

CNT tend to form of bundles due to strong inter-tube van der Waals interactions. Such aggregation prevents the formation of a three-dimensional network structure of the tube in the manufacture of a composite material for improving electrical and mechanical properties. The method of stabilizing and dispersing CNT by using surfactant and water-soluble polymer, which is one of the methods of dispersing CNT, confirmed the dispersibility of CNT. After dissolving 2 g of PSS, PVP and Koll as dispersant of CNT into distilled water, CNTs were mechanically dispersed to compare the dispersion states. Dispersion state were compared after 1 hour, 2 minutes, 4 minutes, 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 1 hour, 2 hours, 3 hours, 4 hours, 5 hours and 10 hours after dispersing for 24 hours using PSS, PVP, Koll, Respectively.

Figure 2: CNT aqueous dispersion according to dispersant type

- (a) Initial state and after 2 minutes of CNT aqueous dispersion dispersed with PSS,
- (b) Initial state of CNT aqueous dispersion dispersed with PVP and appearance after 1 minute,
- (c) Initial condition and after 10 hours of CNT aqueous dispersion dispersed with Koll

Figure 2 (a) shows the state immediately after the dispersion using PSS and after 2 minutes, and Figure 2 (b) shows the state immediately after dispersion using PVP, and immediately after dispersion and after 1 minute. When PSS and PVP were used as dispersants, CNT dispersion was not stable and CNT was found to sink immediately. Figure 2 (c) shows the state immediately after dispersion using Koll as a dispersant and after 10 hours. In this case, the CNT did not sink even after 10 hours. The hydrophobic tail of the surfactant molecule was adsorbed on the CNT surface while the hydrophilic group of the surfactant molecule of the surfactant Koll was oriented toward the aqueous phase. Because of this absorption, CNT dispersion can be achieved because it forms an energy barrier to prevent CNT aggregation.

3.1 Electrical properties

Figure 3 shows the electrical conductivity according to the CNT content of CF-CNT nonwoven fabrics prepared by dispersion by mechanical stirring. When the CNT content of CF-CNT nonwoven

fabrics was 0 wt.%, the electrical conductivity was 10.6 S/cm and the electrical conductivity value was increased to 103 S/cm at the CNT content of 20 wt.%. The electrical conductivity was maintained from 20 wt.% to 100 wt.% and the percolation threshold value of CNT can be 20 wt.%. The electrical conductivities of CF-CNT/epoxy and CNT/epoxy composites were compared as shown in the Figure 3. The electrical conductivity of the CNT/epoxy composites manufactured by dispersing with a high pressure homogenizer was the highest at 196.8 S/cm, and the CF-CNT/epoxy composite was 48.5 S/cm. The CF-CNT/CF woven/CF-CNT/epoxy hybrid composite was slightly lower at 35.7 S/cm. The electric conductivity of the CNT Buckypaper manufactured by dispersing with a high pressure homogenizer and the CF-CNT mixed nonwoven fabric were 412.91 S/cm and 103.45 S/cm. The electric conductivity value of the composite material was higher than that of the nonwoven fabric compared to that of nonwoven.

Figure 3: Electrical conductivity of CF-CNT nonwoven fabric according to CNT content

Figure 4: Electrical conductivity of CF and CNT epoxy composites

3.2 Mechanical properties

Table 1 shows Fiber volume fraction and void contents of CF and CNT composites. The fiber volume fraction of composite material was 2~3% when CF-CNT nonwoven fabric and Buckypaper were used. In the VARIM process, the amount of epoxy resin injected was too much compared to the amount of nonwoven fabric, resulting in a low fiber volume ratio. It was 13% when reinforced with an additional CF woven fabric. Also, the composites of high quality were prepared with low porosity, within 1~3%, of the pore content of all composite material samples.

Table 2 shows tensile strength and tensile modulus of composites. Comparing the CF-CNT/epoxy sample with the CF-CNT/CF W/CF-CNT/epoxy sample reinforced with CF fabric, the laminated sample reinforced with CF fabric was larger at 187.52 MPa. Comparing CF-CNT/epoxy samples with CF-CNT/CF W/CF-CNT/epoxy specimens reinforced with CF fabrics, the laminated sample reinforced with CF fabrics was 187.52 MPa more. The mechanical properties of composites depend not only on the properties of the constituent materials but also on the properties of interfacial bonding and on the mechanism of load transfer. Interfacial strength at the interface between the fiber and the matrix is important, because the epoxy is not sufficiently impregnated into the CF and CNT, resulting

in low interfacial strength and low tensile strength [11]. The CNT Buckypaper/epoxy samples exhibited a tensile strength of 158.20 MPa and a tensile modulus of 16.70 GPa higher than the CF-CNT mixed sheet.

Sample	Thickness (mm)	V _f (%)	V _v (%)
CF-CNT/Epox	0.56	2.62	2.88
CF-CNT/CNT W/CF-CNT/Epox	1.15	13.49	1.42
CNT Buckypaper/Epox	0.32	4.30	1.49

Table 1: Fiber volume fraction and void contents of CF and CNT composites

Sample	Thickness (mm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)
CF-CNT/Epox	0.56	45.17	2.25
CF-CNT/CF W/CF-CNT/Epox	1.15	187.52	20.01
CNT Buckypaper/Epox	0.32	158.20	16.70

Table 2: Tensile properties of CF_CNT and CNT epoxy composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

When the CNT content of CF-CNT nonwovens was 0 wt.%, the electrical conductivity was 10.6 S/cm and the electrical conductivity value was increased to 103 S/cm at the CNT content of 20 wt.%. The electrical conductivity is maintained from 20 wt.% to 100 wt.% and the percolation threshold value of CNT can be 20 wt.%. In the CNT buckypaper, the electric performance could be further enhanced by using high pressure homogenizer, adding various additives, and treating CNT buckypaper surfaces. The electrical conductivity of the CNT buckypaper showed a maximum of 623 S/cm and the electromagnetic shielding property of 35 SE. The epoxy thermoset composites were made with VARIM (Vacuum assisted resin infusion molding) reinforced by the CF nonwovens, CF-CNT nonwovens, CF-CNT nonwoven/CF woven fabrics, and CNT buckypaper. Their mechanical properties shows 56.4, 45.2, 187.5, and 158.2 MPa for the tensile strength and 6.2, 2.3, 20, and 16.7 GPa of tensile modulus, respectively. This research succeeds to demonstrate the potential of CF and CNT reinforced composites as light weight and EMI materials in an interior and structural applications for transportation by presenting the excellent performance in the mechanical and EMI properties.

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